

Table 1. Method, time, and rate of N application at 2 sites in Bangladesh.

Treatment ^a	Portion at time of application ^b				Basal application	N rate (kg/ha)	
	Basal	15 DT	30 DT	5-7 DBPI		Boro	Aus/Aman
Control	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
U11	1/3	—	1/3	1/3	B&I	31	31
U12	1/3	—	1/3	1/3	B&I	62	62
U13	1/3	—	1/3	1/3	B&I	93	93
U14	1/3	—	1/3	1/3	B&I	155	124
U21	—	—	1/2	1/2	—	31	31
U22	—	—	1/2	1/2	—	62	62
U23	—	—	1/2	1/2	—	93	93
U24	—	—	1/2	1/2	—	155	124
USG11	All	—	—	—	DP	31	31
USG12	All	—	—	—	DP	62	62
USG13	All	—	—	—	DP	93	93
USG14	All	—	—	—	DP	155	124
U32	—	1/3	1/3	1/3	—	62	62
USG22	1/2	—	—	1/2	DP	62	62
SCU12	All	—	—	—	B&I	62	62

^a U = prilled urea, USG = urea supergranule (1G.), and SCU = sulfur-coated urea. ^b Basal = immediately before transplanting for B&I and immediately after for DP, DT = days after transplanting, DBPI = days before panicle initiation, B&I = broadcast and incorporated during final land preparation, DP = deep point, after pushing into mud to depth of 10 cm.

Table 2. Effect of N application levels and methods on rice grain yield on 2 Bangladesh soils. ^a

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)													
	Mymensingh				Madhupur									
	Boro	Aus	Aman	Mean	Boro	Aus	Aman	Mean						
Control	3.0	e	1.7	h	3.1	c	2.6	2.1	jk	3.0	g	4.4	g	3.2
U11	3.5	de	2.4	fg	3.4	ab	3.1	2.8	hi	3.0	g	5.0	def	3.6
U12	4.5	cd	2.5	ef	3.5	ab	3.5	3.5	fg	3.4	defg	4.9	f	3.9
U13	5.8	ab	2.7	def	3.5	ab	4.0	3.4	gh	3.5	cdefg	5.5	abc	4.1
U14	6.5	a	3.2	abcd	3.5	ab	4.4	5.7	ab	3.8	abcd	5.8	ab	5.1
U21	3.6	de	2.6	ef	3.3	bc	3.2	2.7	ij	3.1	fg	5.4	abcd	3.7
U22	4.0	cde	2.8	def	3.5	ab	3.4	3.5	fg	3.6	abcde	5.2	cd	4.1
U23	4.3	cd	3.3	abc	3.5	ab	3.7	4.1	ef	3.7	abcd	5.5	abc	4.4
U24	6.0	ab	3.4	ab	3.5	ab	4.3	5.3	b	4.1	a	5.5	abc	5.0
USG11	4.2	cde	2.6	ef	3.5	ab	3.4	3.6	fg	3.3	defg	5.4	bcde	4.1
USG12	5.1	bc	2.9	bcde	3.5	ab	3.9	4.7	cde	3.3	defg	5.6	abc	4.5
USG13	6.1	ab	3.6	a	3.5	ab	4.4	4.8	cd	4.0	abc	5.8	ab	4.8
USG14	6.8	a	3.5	a	3.7	a	4.7	6.2	a	4.0	ab	5.9	a	5.4
U32	3.4	de	2.8	cde	3.3	bc	3.2	2.8	i	3.3	defg	5.3	cdef	3.8
USG22	4.3	cd	3.0	bcde	3.4	ab	3.6	4.6	de	3.6	bcdef	5.2	cdef	4.5
SCU12	3.4	de	1.9	gh	3.4	bc	2.9	2.0	k	3.1	efg	5.0	ef	3.4

^a Figures in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other.

meq/100 g soil, and 10-12-2.2 ppm available P-S-Zn. Soil at Madhupur was a silt loam with pH 5.7, 0.50% organic C, CEC and exchangeable K 7.2 and 0.17 meq/100 g soil, and 149-3.1 ppm available P-S-Zn. Time, method, and placement of N fertilizer is in Table 1. Each plot received a basal application of 20-30-20-5 kg P-K-S-Zn/ha.

Grain yield data for both sites are in Table 2. Treatment effects were significantly different in all crops. Usually, yield increased with increasing N application up to 155 or 124 kg N/ha regardless of management.

Single deep point placement of urea supergranules (USG) was superior to equal amounts of prilled urea (PU) applied in 2 or 3 splits in both soils. USG superiority was most pronounced in boro, perhaps because there was greater horizontal and upward movement of N from deep-placed USG in boro, which resulted in better N utilization. Broadcast, split-applied PU may have had higher volatilization losses in the alternate wetting and drying in boro.

Averaging data from three rice crops showed USG performed best at all N doses (Table 2). In both soils, USG at 62 kg N/ha gave the highest grain production per kg N applied. Sulfur-coated urea produced the lowest yields at both sites. *ℳ*

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Effect of crop establishment techniques and seed rate on upland rice yield and weed growth

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Upland rice farmers in Nigeria generally dibble rice seeds at no specific seed rate

after land preparation. To determine the effect of establishment methods on rice yield and weed growth, three crop establishment methods (broadcasting, dibbling, and drilling) were tried at 45, 90, or 135 kg seeds/ha under upland conditions.

The experiment was in a split-plot, randomized block design with three replications. Establishment techniques

Table 1. Effect of seed rate on weed growth and yield of FARO 11, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Seed rate (kg/ha)	Dry weed weight (g/m ²)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
45	0.51	1.1
90	0.39	0.9
135	0.35	0.7
LSD	0.05	0.3

^a Drought at flowering stage caused generally poor grain yield.

formed the main plot and seed rates the subplot. Seeds of FARO 11 were drilled along furrows made 25 cm apart or dibbled 25 cm within and between rows.

For initial weed control, a combination of thiobencarb + propanil at 3 kg ai/ha was applied to all treatments 7 d after sowing. Weed weight and grain yield were determined at maturity and grain yield was adjusted to 14% moisture content.

Seed rate and crop establishment

techniques did not significantly reduce weed weight; however, weed weight declined progressively as seed rate increased.

Highest yield was with 45 kg seeds/ha (Table 1), probably because of less competition among rice plants than at higher rates. Crop establishment techniques did not significantly affect grain yield (Table 2); however, dibbling gave the highest yield. *S*

Table 2. Effect of crop establishment techniques on weed growth and yield of FARO 11, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Establishment method	Dry weed weight (g/m ²)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
Drilling	0.43	0.8
Dibbling	0.63	1.0
Broadcasting	0.19	0.7
LSD	0.05	0.4

^a Drought at flowering stage caused generally poor grain yield.

Response of lowland rice to phosphorus fertilizer

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Next to N, P is the second major nutrient element that limits rice yield. Response to P varies with soil characteristics. In Punjab, the rice area has expanded to include light-textured soils that often are P deficient. We studied the response of rice to P in farmer fields at five sites around the State. Soil characteristics of the fields are given in Table 1. N at 120 kg/ha was applied to all fields in 3 equal splits. Different levels of P and 12.5 kg K/ha were incorporated during the last puddling, and 35-d-old PR106 seedlings were transplanted.

Applying 13.5 kg P/ha increased rice

Table 1. Chemical characteristics of soils at five sites in the Punjab.

Classification	Texture	pH	Organic C (%)	EC (mmho/cm)	Available P (kg/ha)
Haplustalf	Sandy loam	8.4	0.54	0.35	5.6
Ustochrept	Sandy loam	8.4	0.65	0.38	38.8
Haplustalf	Sandy loam	8.3	0.51	0.40	11.6
Ustochrept	Sandy loam	9.0	0.40	0.24	1.8
Ustochrept	Clay loam	8.5	0.41	0.35	12.1

yield by 300 to 740 kg/ha at 3 sites, but the differences were not significant. At 2 sites, there was a significant response to 19.5 kg P/ha. Mean values for all sites showed that applying 19.5 kg P/ha increase rice yield by 330 kg (Table 2). Rice did not respond to 26 kg P/ha.

Although the response to fertilizer P was not substantial, the results indicate that P application is necessary to achieve optimum rice yield in Punjab. Because rice - wheat is a common rotation, P not utilized by the rice crop

Table 2. Response of rice to fertilizer P at 5 sites in the Punjab.

P (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)					
	1	2	3	4	5	Mean
0	8.0	8.5	6.9	6.8	1.2	7.5
13.5	8.4	9.3	6.8	1.0	1.5	1.8
19.5	1.9	9.2	1.6	1.2	1.5	1.8
26.0	8.5	9.0	1.5	1.2	1.1	7.9
CD at 5%	ns	ns	0.5	0.2	ns	

is utilized by the succeeding wheat crop. *S*

Effect of split-applied N on rice yields

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We evaluated the effect of split application of N fertilizer on rice yield at TNRRI. Nine N application times were tested with ADT36 (105-110 d variety) in 1984 wet season (Jun-Sep) in a randomized block design. Soil was clay loam with 0.13% N, 1.2% organic matter, and cation exchange capacity 23 ml/litre.

Prilled urea (at 75 kg N/ha) was applied in 2 or 3 splits at planting, 5 d after transplanting (DT), 10 DT, and 15 DT with 50 + 25 + 25% splits or 4 equal splits. This was compared with 0 fertilizer N and all basal N. PK at 38 kg was applied to all plots.

Grain yield was maximum (5.4 t/ha) with 3 splits (see table), and was significantly superior to that of both checks.

Basal 25% N appeared adequate if applied before 10 DT followed by splits. Basal 50% N was also adequate if applied after 10 DT and followed by splits. *S*

Effect of split application of 75 kg N/ha on grain yield of a short-duration rice variety, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
0 N (check)	3.6 h
All N at planting (check)	4.4 g
50% at planting + 2 equal splits	4.9 ef
25% at planting + 2 equal splits	5.1 bcd
50% at 5 DT + 2 equal splits	5.2 abcd
25% at 5 DT + 3 equal splits	5.3 ab
50% at 10 DT + 2 equal splits	5.4 a
25% at 10 DT + 3 equal splits	5.0 def
50% at 15 DT + 2 equal splits	5.0 def
25% at 15 DT + 3 equal splits	4.8 f

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.